

On-board smartphone micromotor-based fluorescence assays

Kaisong Yuan,^a Víctor de la Asunción-Nadal,^a Carmen Cuntín-Abal,^a Beatriz Jurado-Sánchez^{a,b*} and Alberto Escarpa^{a,b*}

Received 00th January 20xx,
Accepted 00th January 20xx

DOI: 10.1039/x0xx00000x

Herein, we describe the design of a portable device integrating micromotors for real-time fluorescence sensing of (bio)markers. The system comprises a universal 3D printed platform to hold a commercial smartphone, which is equipped with an external magnification optical lens (20-400X) and tailor-made emission filters directly attached to the camera, an adjustable sample holder to accommodate a glass slide and laser excitation sources. On a first approach, we illustrate the suitability of the platform using magnetic Janus micromotors modified with fluorescence ZnS@Cd_xSe_{1-x} quantum dots for real-time ON-OFF mercury detection. On a second approach, graphdyne tubular catalytic micromotors modified with a Rhodamine labelled affinity peptide will be used for OFF-ON detection of Cholera Toxin B. The micromotor-based fluorescence smartphone approach was compared to a high-performance optical microscope, obtaining a perfect match. This versatility allows for easy integration of micromotor fluorescence sensing strategies based on different propulsion mechanisms, allowing for its future use on a myriad of biomarkers, and even multiplexed schemes.

1. Introduction

Decentralized health monitoring can aid to reduce the burden in hospitals and primary care units, not to mention the potential use in non-developed countries.^{1, 2} The rise of smartphone technology in connection with point-of-care (POCs) miniaturized biosensors hold considerable promise for novel diagnosis and monitoring platforms.^{3, 4, 5}

Fluorescence optical detection offers great advantages when coupled with smartphone technology, as the built-in cameras can be readily used without the need for additional parts.⁶⁻⁸ POCs integrating lateral flow immunoassays have been applied for the detection of *Escherichia coli*⁹ and methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*¹⁰ bacteria in urine and blood samples, respectively. Similarly, prostate-specific antigen¹¹ or virus detection^{12,13, 14} in whole blood have been achieved in less than 30 min in POCs using microchip-based pre-processing procedures. A real-time fluorescence-based POCs for hemoglobin relies on a specifically designed microchip integrating SiO₂@QDs with acoustofluidic enrichment, achieving detection in whole blood in just 2 min at μg mL⁻¹ levels.¹⁵

Micro- and nanomotors are at the forefront of nanotechnology research and have demonstrated their potential for novel on-the-fly biomarker sensing approaches using ultralow sample and reagent volumes.¹⁶⁻²¹ The motion of micromotor-based

sensor platforms greatly enhances analyte-probe interactions, which along with its possibilities for functionalization and nanoscale dimensions, enable such autonomous micromotors for the design of portable detection devices and future POC systems, that can avoid the need for microchips or other sample preparation steps.²²⁻²⁸ Three strategies based on motion-based detection using smartphones as a detection platform have been reported. Yet, fluorescence monitoring either on the micromotor surface or in the solution using portable devices remains unexplored. Regarding the previous reports, firstly, HIV-1 virus detection has been achieved using a portable device integrating a microchip and DNA-modified platinum-gold Janus micromotors. The micromotors can move in peroxide solutions by decomposition of such fuel in the catalytic Pt part and generation of oxygen bubbles. The detection principle involves loop-mediated isothermal amplification of the nucleic acid of HIV-1, followed by mixing of resulting amplicons with the DNA-modified micromotors. The presence of HIV-1 generates large amplicons that reduce the initial speed of the motors (turn-off). Such decrease is used as the analytical signal, detecting 1000 virus particles mL⁻¹ in 60 min.²⁹ Additionally, a similar micromotor-based POC was also applied for Zika virus detection in a turn-on configuration. In this case, the Au Janus micromotors are modified with anti-Zika virus monoclonal antibodies for virus capture, followed by the attachment of anti-Zika antibody platinum nanoparticles. The presence of virus in a sample results in the accumulation of an increased concentration of Pt beads, increasing the speed in peroxide solutions.³⁰ Finally, our group has reported a motion-based sensing smartphone for glutathione detection, in this case, the speed of the micromotors decreases due to a thiol-mediated poisoning of the catalyst in presence of the analyte.³¹ Despite its simplicity, such POCs requires a sophisticated sample pre-

^a Department of Analytical Chemistry, Physical Chemistry and Chemical Engineering, University of Alcalá, Alcalá de Henares E-28871, Madrid, Spain. E-mail: beatriz.jurado@uah.es, alberto.escarpa@uah.es (Tel: +34 91 8854995).

^b Chemical Research Institute "Andrés M. del Río", University of Alcalá, Alcalá de Henares E-28871, Madrid, Spain Address here.

Electronic Supplementary Information (ESI) available: Supporting Table and Videos. See DOI: 10.1039/x0xx00000x

treatment and detection algorithms for motion detection as no visual detection is available.

Herein, we describe the design of a smartphone-based device integrating micromotors for real-time fluorescence assays. To date, one inherent limitation of the use of self-propelled micromotors for fluorescence detection -unlike the motion-based strategies discussed above- is that all approaches are performed using high performance optical microscopes, which still requires trained personnel, yet it is a bulk sophisticated and expensive instrumentation hampering on site analysis. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first smartphone-based portable device used in connection with micromotors for point of need testing, revealing the novelty and pertinent utility of it, solving a main technical drawback in the field. The system herein reported comprises a 3D dark platform integrating a smartphone coupled with a high-resolution optical lens, custom made emission filters and a compartment for insertion of low-cost commercial lasers to tailor the excitation wavelength. The system integrates a movable custom-made platform for the insertion of a glass slide to place the sample and the micromotors. The platform allows for fast sample focus to obtain high resolution images which are further processed. To demonstrate the suitability of the universal micromotor based device, relevant proof of the concept applications were chosen covering both, Janus and tubular micromotors under magnetic and catalytic motion, respectively. On a first approach, we will illustrate the suitability of the device using magnetic Janus micromotors modified with fluorescence ZnS@Cd_xSe_{1-x} QDs for real-time ON-OFF mercury detection. On a second approach, graphdyne (GDY) tubular catalytic micromotors modified with a Rhodamine labelled affinity peptide are used for OFF-ON detection of Cholera toxin B (CTB). The suitability of the detection protocols was validated against a high-resolution optical microscope, with excellent match. Compared with previous POCs approaches, our strategy allows for direct detection using just microliter of sample and micromotors, replacing semi-quantitative paper-based strips or complex microchips. The versatility of the strategy allows for easy integration of micromotor sensing strategies based on different propulsion mechanism (catalytic, magnetic, ultrasound) relying in fluorescence detection of a myriad of biomarkers, and even multiplexed schemes.

2. Materials and methods

Smartphone-fluorescence device. The 3D printed micromotor based fluorescence set-up was designed using SolidWorks. The platform contains an aperture to insert different laser sources at the desired excitation wavelengths, along with a sample holder to place a glass slide with the drop containing the sample. The laser beam direction is parallel to the sample. Different cut-off emission filters (red, green or yellow) were placed prior a 20X-400X Universal Tip scope used for magnification (which is directly attached to a smartphone). Both components were purchased from Amazon. Micromotors motion and/or the fluorescence of the solution were directly observed in the camera application of the phone, which was also used to record the Videos at 30 FPS. Micromotor motion was tracked with ImageJ (https://imagej.net/Particle_Tracker) and fluorescence

measurements were performed using Fiji free software. An inverted optical microscope (Nikon Eclipse Instrument Inc. TiS/L100) coupled with fluorescence filter cubes (FITC, λ_{ex} , 467 nm; λ_{em} , 498 nm and G-2A, λ_{ex} , 510, λ_{em} , 560 nm) and a Zyla CMOS digital camera was used to validate the smartphone platform. Images or movies were processed using Image J and Fiji software, respectively.

Magnetic set-up for magnetic micromotor movement. A customized system comprising a permanent magnet attached to an electric motor with a permanent magnet is used to create a rotatory magnetic field. The motor is assembled in a platform that fits the glass slide placed in the sample holder. The speed of the electric motor can be modulated to control the frequency of the magnetic field (from 0 to 9 Hz) and in turn, the speed of the micromotors.

Mercury detection assay principle. Scheme 1 shows the principle of Hg detection using the quantum dots (QDs) modified Janus micromotors. For detection, 1 μ L of modified Janus micromotor solution was placed on the glass slide which was next assembled into the holder. The drop was mixed with solutions containing increasing concentrations (from 0 to 1 μ g mL⁻¹) of Hg²⁺ (cat. Y0002003). The magnetic module was placed below and the frequency set to 4 Hz. Next, the solution was irradiated with the laser and videos were recorded directly with the camera of the phone. The experiments were performed in a similar fashion using the optical microscope for comparison.

Scheme 1. Principle of the assay for Hg detection using ZnS@Cd_xSe_{1-x} modified Janus micromotors moving under the action of magnetic fields (A) and in static mode (B).

As can be seen in Scheme 1 (A), micromotors are modified with ZnS@Cd_xSe_{1-x} QDs and thus, present an intense fluorescence emission at 490 nm (ON state). The propulsion by the action of magnetic field in samples containing Hg²⁺, there is an ionic exchange-replacement of Zn atoms in the QDs by Hg ions, leading to the generation of non-fluorescence HgS@Cd_xSe_{1-x} QDs (OFF state). In the absence of propulsion/magnetic fields (static mode, Scheme 1, B) no fluorescence quenching is observed due to there is no fluid mixing and the Hg ions do not interact with the QDs and the micromotors, preventing thus the quenching of fluorescence. Fluorescence of the micromotors in all cases was evaluated by taking time-lapse images, which were transferred to a computer using the Wi-Fi connectivity of the

smartphone and processes with Fiji software for uniformity. The analytical performance was evaluated through the limit of detection (LOD), limit of quantification (LOQ), selectivity and recovery. Calibrations plots were obtained ($n=3$) and the LOD or LOQ were calculated as 3 or 10 times the standard deviation of the intercept divided by the slope of the calibration linear fit. Two different micromotors batches were used for evaluation. Selectivity was evaluated against $1 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of potentially interfering species including Ca, Cd, Mn, Ni and Zn ions. Recovery was evaluated by fortifying raw (undiluted) human serum samples (cat. H4522) with $1 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of Hg^{2+} .

Toxin detection assay principle. Scheme 2 shows the principle of CTB detection using the GDY tubular micromotors. $1 \mu\text{L}$ of modified motors, $1 \mu\text{L}$ of H_2O_2 3% and $1 \mu\text{L}$ of sample or solutions containing increasing concentrations (from 0 to 5 ng mL^{-1}) of CTB (cat. C9903) were mixed on the glass slide. Sample was next irradiated with the laser and Videos recorded and processed in a similar fashion to that reported for mercury. Experiments were also performed with the optical microscope for comparison.

Scheme 2. Principle of the assay for CTB detection using affinity peptide modified GDY tubular micromotors.

As can be seen in Scheme 2, micromotors are modified with the specific peptide for CTB as representative toxin, which is labelled with fluorescence rhodamine. In the initial state, the peptide is immobilized in the micromotor by incubation. The peptide interacts with the outer GDY micromotor layer by π - π stacking, resulting in the quenching of the native fluorescence of the peptide (OFF state). Under the presence of the specific CTB, the higher affinity of the peptide for the specific analyte results in its desorption from the GDY surface, leading to a strong fluorescence in the solution (ON state). In the absence of peroxide/autonomous propulsion, no fluorescence recovery is observed due to there is no fluid mixing and the specific toxin do not interact with the peptide-modified micromotors. Analytical performance was evaluated in a similar fashion to that

described for Hg ion. Selectivity was evaluated using endotoxin from *Escherichia coli* (cat. L2630) and bovine serum albumin (cat. A2153) as potential interfering compounds.

3. Results and discussion

Figure 1A depicts the concept of micromotor based platform. As can be seen, a tailor-made 3D platform integrates all the components required to perform the fluorescence detection measurements. To perform the detection, the sample containing the micromotors is placed on a glass slide, which is assembled in a movable platform which allow for fast focus like that performed in normal microscopes. Next, the sample is irradiated with a commercial laser at a desired wavelength in parallel. In this way, sample is excited and the released fluorescence travels to the objective/camera of an iPhone, which is equipped with a high-resolution lens and a tailor-made emission filter at the desired wavelength. Videos are directly recorded with the phone and further processes with Fiji software, as already described in the experimental section. Figure 1B shows pictures of the attachment among the filters and the optical lens. In this case, red, green and yellow filters were obtained from Amazon and cut to fit the objective of the phone. The strategy is highly versatile and allow to use more types of filters and shapes to fit several smartphones. The pictures also illustrate the irradiation of the sample with the laser. Please note here that we open the platform to take the pictures, but for real fluorescence measurements all is covered and, in the dark, to avoid potential interferences with the signal. Figure 1C shows a real image of the displayed contents in the smartphone screen during a measurement. The platform is highly versatile, allowing for its usage with catalytic, magnetic, light or ultrasound propelled micromotors. To illustrate the concept, we select fluorescence detection applications using tubular and Janus micromotors with catalytic and magnetic propulsion modes, respectively. Thus, Figure 1C and D illustrate real images from the smartphone using peptide modified tubular micromotors for OFF-ON toxin detection and QDs modified magnetic Janus micromotors for ON-OFF mercury detection. As can be seen, in the tubular micromotors red fluorescence, arising from the Rhodamine labelled peptide probe is noted in the figure and supporting Video S1, which is not observed when the laser excitation is turned off. In the case of magnetic Janus, the micromotors observed in the figure are clearly fluorescence due to the modification with the QDs. As in the previous case, no light is emitted after turning the laser off (see Video S1). In brief, the images illustrate a clear fluorescence in the tubular micromotors solution (due to Rhodamine labelled peptide probe) or in the Janus micromotors (due to QDs), allowing to perform detection both in the solution and in the micromotors. Such configuration greatly simplifies the strategy, avoiding the use of microchips or other sample pre-processing attachments. Indeed, the micromotors can act as mobile (bio)-sensors, allowing to perform fast, on-the-fly detection, in real time and with low sample and reagents requirements. The device is also extremely useful to

imaging other fluorescence species such as QDs (see **Figure 1D**, right).

Prior application for the detection of target analytes, the performance of the system and the excitation-emission configuration based on laser and filters, respectively, was evaluated. First, the absorbance spectra of each filter were evaluated with UV/VIS measurements by placing it in front of the beam of a spectrophotometer. Data was processed to obtain the transmittance spectra, which is illustrated in **Figure S1, A**. Once characterized, appropriate commercial $\text{Cd}_x\text{Se}_{1-x}$ @ZnS QDs with tailored sizes and, in turn, emission and

excitation profiles, were chosen and measured in solution and incorporated in the micromotors. Images were taken according to the conditions schematically summarized in **Figure S1, B** and processed with Fiji software to obtain the histograms both background (B in the figure) and the fluorescence part in the sample (S in the figure). For both solutions and micromotors and in all configurations, histograms indicate that the settings are suitable because the fluorescence emission presents higher brightness than the noise, including dark-current noise and background fluorescence, with no overexposure.⁶

Figure 1. Smartphone-based fluorescence platform integrating micromotors and proof-of-concept applications. A) Integration of the smartphone into a 3D printed platform and description of the different parts of the device. B) Detailed pictures of the assembly of the optical lens with the different filters (a), detailed size of the tailor-made absorbance filters (b), the filter on top of the camera of the phone (c) and irradiation of the sample -deposited on a glass slide- with the specific laser. C) Picture of the screen on the phone showing the real time fluorescence detection with moving tubular (catalytic) micromotors. D) Time lapse images (Taken from Video S1) showing the movement and fluorescence of microliter drops containing bubble-propelled GDY/Pt tubular micromotors modified with a specific fluorescence probe for OFF-ON detection of CTB (λ_{ex} , 532 nm; λ_{em} , 665 nm), magnetic actuated $\text{ZnS}@Cd_x\text{Se}_{1-x}/\text{GO}/\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ Janus micromotors for ON-OFF detection of Hg^{2+} (λ_{ex} , 405 nm; λ_{em} , 495 nm), drops of core-shell $\text{ZnS}@Cd_x\text{Se}_{1-x}$ QDs (top: λ_{ex} , 405 nm; λ_{em} , 574 nm; bottom: λ_{ex} , 405 nm; λ_{em} , 525 nm). White circles indicate a micromotor moving. Scale bars, 50 μm .

Once demonstrated the suitability of the set-up, the platform was evaluated first for ON-OFF detection approaches, using Hg^{2+} as proof of concept and inspired in a previous work from our research group.³² For the application we select $\text{ZnS}@Cd_x\text{Se}_{1-x}/\text{GO}/\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ Janus micromotors due to its relatively bigger size (20 μm) compared to tubular and other design due to an optimal size which allow for better area selection for accurate fluorescence measurements. The strategy is depicted in **Figure 2A**. In brief, initially the micromotors exhibit a strong fluorescence arising from the QDs. After Hg^{2+} addition and 2 minutes of the micromotor movement the fluorescence is quenched due to cationic

exchange and/or Hg ion attachment to the outer ZnS layer in the QDs, generating $\text{HgS}@Cd_x\text{Se}_{1-x}$ or alloyed $\text{Zn}_{1-x}\text{Hg}_x@Cd_x\text{Se}_{1-x}$ QDs and displacing the emission wavelength, resulting in fluorescence quenching in a concentration-dependence manner.³²⁻³⁴ Such change can be clearly observed in solutions containing 1 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of Hg^{2+} (insets of **Figure 2A** and **Video S2**), with a clear initial fluorescence emission which is gradually quenched and the micromotors turn into a violet color, similar to that observed to the blank, due to reflection from the laser source. To facilitate fluorescence measurement, images were converted into black and white scale, further confirming the absence of fluorescence in the quenched micromotors. In this case, to illustrate the versatility of the micromotor based

ARTICLE

platform, we select magnetic propulsion mode in serum samples to illustrate the concept. Such configuration can be ideal to perform detection of relevant biomarkers in fluids such as whole blood samples, in which the high content of catalase, hemoglobin and proteins hamper the applicability of catalytic propelled designs, the most used to date for analytical purposes.³⁵ To perform the experiment, the magnetic set-up (see the experimental section for further details) was placed **below** the platform and close to the sample holder containing the glass slide with the micromotors. The platform allows to tailor the speed of the micromotors by changing the frequency of the magnetic field (from 0 to 9 Hz). Speed increase along frequency up to 4 Hz from 0 to $40 \pm 5 \mu\text{m s}^{-1}$. Higher frequencies generate turbulent flows that decrease the speed up to 2 times, with an unstable pattern. As such, frequency of the magnetic field was set to 4 Hz. Next, we performed control experiments to check the role of micromotor movement in the detection. To this end, static ZnS@Cd_xSe_{1-x}/GO/Fe₂O₃ micromotors were incubated with $1 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of Hg²⁺ and Videos were recorded for 1 hour. Negligible fluorescence quenching is noted (not shown), revealing the crucial movement of the micromotors to accelerate detection. Next, we evaluated the selectivity of the protocol for Hg²⁺ sensing. As can be seen in the normalized fluorescence plot of **Figure 2B** and corresponding time-lapse images, fluorescence quenching is only observed in the presence of the target analyte, with negligible changes in the

presence of potentially interfering cations, probably due its lower affinity to undergo cation exchange with the QDs or no disruption of the fluorescence signal. To validate the strategy, experiments were also performed with a high-resolution optical microscope, obtaining the similar results. Next, calibration plots were evaluated with both instrumental set-ups using the micromotors and increasing concentrations of Hg²⁺. As can be seen, on both cases, the fluorescence of the micromotors decrease as the concentration of the target analyte increase. The LODs were 0.09 and $0.08 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ calculated using the microscope and the smartphone platform, respectively. The linear range spans from 0.25 to $1 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ on both cases. Next, we evaluate the performance of the strategy by performing recovery studies in raw serum samples as representative biological fluid. Recovery percentages of 93 ± 5 and 89 ± 5 were obtained with the device and the microscope, respectively, illustrating the suitability of the platform for future ions detections as hazardous in complex biological fluids. Similar results were observed using two different micromotor batches. Please note here that despite the LOD for Hg²⁺ detection is relatively high, our aim here was to demonstrate the integration and feasibility of being able to carry out Hg detection using fluorescent Janus micromotors on board on a smartphone. For further applications, the micromotors can be modified with specific probes to increase the sensitivity in the detection.

Figure 2. ON-OFF magnetic actuated ZnS@Cd_xSe_{1-x}/GO/Fe₂O₃ Janus micromotors strategy for Hg²⁺ detection using the fluorescence smartphone. A) Schematic of the sensing strategy and corresponding time-lapse microscopy images (taken from Video S2) before and after micromotor navigation in solutions containing $1 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of Hg²⁺. B) Selectivity of the sensing strategy in the presence of heavy metals and corresponding real time-lapse fluorescence images using the smartphone (top) and a high-performance optical microscope (bottom). C) Time-lapse fluorescence images of the moving micromotors in the presence of increasing concentrations of Hg²⁺ taken using the smartphone (λ_{ex} , 405 nm; λ_{em} , 495 nm) and the microscope and corresponding calibration plots. Scale bars, 50 μm .

Figure 3. A) OFF-ON GDY/Pt tubular micromotors modified with a Rhodamine-labeled affinity peptide for CTB detection. B) Specificity of the sensing strategy under the presence of the target toxin, endotoxin from *Escherichia coli* (LPS) and bovine serum albumin (BSA). C) Time-lapse fluorescence images of the moving micromotors in the presence of increasing concentrations of CTB taken using the smartphone (λ_{ex} , 532 nm; λ_{em} , 665 nm) and the microscope and corresponding calibration plots.

As a second proof-of-concept application, we evaluated the utility of the platform for OFF-ON micromotor based approaches, which is an important configuration for the analysis of clinical biomarkers with excellent performance and negligible sample consumption. Yet, to date, the practical utility of such procedures is hampered by the requirements for the use of high-resolution fluorescence microscopes. As such, the integration into simple and portable instrumentation such as the one described here will bring closer the strategies for practical use in future personalized medicine. The concept of the strategy is depicted in **Figure 3A** and relies on the functionalization of tubular micromotors with fluorescence labelled receptors. In the presence of the target analyte, such receptors are released in a concentration dependence manner. Thus, toxins,³⁶ miRNA,³⁷ proteins³⁸ or bacterial endotoxins have been detected using such configurations and graphene³⁶ or chalcogenides based micromotors.³⁸

As model system in the work we selected CTB as target analytes and affinity peptide modified GDY/Pt tubular micromotors, following a

very recent approach developed by our research group.³⁹ CTB is an integral part of the toxin produced by *Vibrio Cholerae* bacteria and can cause severe health effect such as severe diarrhea.⁴⁰ As described in the experimental section, the affinity peptide is specifically designed as a fingerprint of the CTB. Such peptide can be incorporated on the surface of GDY micromotors by physical adsorption through electrostatic and π -stacking with the non-polar and aromatic amino acids present in the peptide (arginine, cysteine, alanine, proline, lysine) and through the p-orbitals in the aromatic rhodamine B tag. Under the presence of the target CTB, a competitive binding is established and the higher affinity of the peptide toward the analyte results in its release from the GDY surface, increasing thus the fluorescence in the solution in just 3 minutes.^{39, 41} The specificity of the protocol is clearly illustrated in the normalized fluorescence plot of **Figure 3B**, which indicate only fluorescence increase under the presence of CTB, with no changes produced by other interfering species such as BSA and endotoxins from *Escherichia coli*. Fluorescence images were taken both with the

smartphone platform and with a high-resolution optical microscope, with similar results on both cases. Control experiments using static modified micromotors were also performed, with negligible fluorescence recovery (18%), illustrating again the crucial role of micromotor movement in accelerating and enhancing the detection performance. To further evaluate the biosensing capacity and performance of the integrated platform, calibration plots were taken. The experiments were repeated in parallel using the high-resolution optical microscope for comparison (see **Figure 3C**). The calculated LODs were 1.6 and 1.4 ng mL⁻¹ for the smartphone platform and the high-resolution optical microscope, respectively. Linear range spans from 4.5 to 5000 ng mL⁻¹ of both cases, with an excellent match, which further illustrate the practical utility of the developed protocol. Excellent recoveries close to 100 % in fortified serum samples were also obtained. Similar results were observed using two different micromotor batches. Indeed, the LOD and LOQ are much lower than the concentration of cholera toxin in ill patients, revealing the suitability for future diagnosis of such disease. While catalytic micromotors are used here, the strategy can be translated to magnetic configurations (as illustrated for Hg²⁺ detection) and receptors for a myriad of applications only limited by our imagination.

4. Conclusions

We have demonstrated here, for the first time, the feasibility of a smartphone-based-platform integrating micromotors for on-the-fly (bio)-sensing approaches. Technically, the coupling of high magnifications lens, tailor made emission filters and excitation lasers with a smartphone-results in a highly efficient optical device that can be used by non-specialized personnel and in an easy manner. The technological suitability of the strategy was revealed by the close match with the results obtained using high-resolution optical microscope. As such, the work addresses the important drawback existing to date for the application of highly efficient micromotors strategies for biomarker detection, that require the use of sophisticated and expensive instrumentation not available in routine laboratories. The analytical versatility of the platform in terms of types of micromotors, propulsion modes and fluorescence strategies have been clearly illustrated by the detection of Hg²⁺ ions and CTB, using serum as common matrix. The detection can be performed in less than 5 minutes and just require dropping the sample (human serum) on a glass slide along with the micromotor and fuel solution, with an average cost of 0.5 € per analysis. Data can be easily sent to a server cloud and computer for processing. In future works, a more sophisticated algorithm can be also developed for direct analysis and processing using just the smartphone. Technologically speaking, the characteristics of the proposed platform constitute by themselves a clear step ahead to achieve those required by the World Health Organization's criteria (affordable, sensitive, specific, user friendly, rapid, equipment-free). Compared with existing POCs for clinical biomarkers based on fluorescence detection (see **Table S1** in the Supporting information), our system simplified the designs, avoiding the use of sample pre-processing microchips or other steps, reducing the detection time and with adequate LODs. Future aims should be focused to tailor the strategy for other configurations and other receptors, increasing the overall sensitivity of the system.

Author Contributions

K. Yuan: Conceptualization; Data Curation; Formal analysis; Investigation; Visualization; Writing - original draft; Writing - review & editing. **V. A. Nadal:** Conceptualization; Data Curation; Formal Analysis; Investigation; Visualization; Writing - review & editing. **C. Cuntín-Abal:** Writing - review & editing. **B. Jurado-Sánchez:** Conceptualization; Data Curation; Formal analysis; Visualization; Writing - original draft; Writing - review & editing; Funding acquisition; Supervision. **A. Escarpa:** Conceptualization; Data Curation; Formal analysis; Visualization; Writing - review & editing; Resources; Funding acquisition; Supervision.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the Community of Madrid [TRANSNANOAVANSENS, S2018/NMT-4349 (A.E), [CM/JIN/2019-007](#) (B.J.S) and PEJ-2020-AI/IND-17560 (C.C.A)]; University of Alcala [FPI fellowship, V.A.N]; the Spanish Ministry of Economy, Industry and Competitiveness [grant numbers [RYC-2015-17558](#), co-financed by EU (B.J.S, K.Y), CTQ2017-86441-C2-1-R (A.E)] and the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation [grant number PID2020-118154GB-I00, (A. E and B.J.S)].

References

1. X. Ding, M. G. Mauk, K. Yin, K. Kadimisetty and C. Liu, *Anal Chem*, 2019, **91**, 655-672.
2. A. Malekjahani, S. Sindhvani, A. M. Syed and W. C. W. Chan, *Acc Chem Res*, 2019, **52**, 2406-2414.
3. M. Rezazadeh, S. Seidi, M. Lid, S. Pedersen-Bjergaard and Y. Yamini, *Trends Anal Chem*, 2019, **118**, 548-555.
4. W. Zhao, S. Tian, L. Huang, K. Liu, L. Dong and J. Guo, *Analyst*, 2020, **145**, 2873-2891.
5. E. Aydingoglan, E. Guler Celik and S. Timur, *Anal Chem*, 2018, **90**, 12325-12333.
6. B. Dai, Z. Jiao, L. Zheng, H. Bachman, Y. Fu, X. Wan, Y. Zhang, Y. Huang, X. Han, C. Zhao, T. J. Huang, S. Zhuang and D. Zhang, *Light Sci Appl*, 2019, **8**, 75.
7. H. Yu, Y. Tan and B. T. Cunningham, *Anal Chem*, 2014, **86**, 8805-8813.
8. Q. Wei, H. Qi, W. Luo, D. Tseng, S. J. Ki, Z. Wan, Z. Göröcs, L. A. Bentolila, T.-T. Wu, R. Sun and A. Ozcan, *ACS Nano*, 2013, **7**, 9147-9155.
9. I. P. Alves and N. M. Reis, *Biosens Bioelectron*, 2019, **145**, 111624.
10. V. K. Rajendran, P. Bakthavathsalam, P. L. Bergquist and A. Sunna, *Sens Act B Chem*, 2019, **298**, 126849.
11. A. I. Barbosa, P. Gehlot, K. Sidapra, A. D. Edwards and N. M. Reis, *Biosens Bioelectron*, 2015, **70**, 5-14.

12. K. Ming, J. Kim, M. J. Biondi, A. Syed, K. Chen, A. Lam, M. Ostrowski, A. Rebbapragada, J. J. Feld and W. C. W. Chan, *ACS Nano*, 2015, **9**, 3060-3074.
13. F. Sun, A. Ganguli, J. Nguyen, R. Brisbin, K. Shanmugam, D. L. Hirschberg, M. B. Wheeler, R. Bashir, D. M. Nash and B. T. Cunningham, *Lab Chip*, 2020, **20**, 1621-1627.
14. F. Hu, J. Li, Z. Zhang, M. Li, S. Zhao, Z. Li and N. Peng, *Anal Chem*, 2020, **92**, 2258-2265.
15. L. Zhang, Z. Tian, H. Bachman, P. Zhang and T. J. Huang, *ACS Nano*, 2020, **14**, 3159-3169.
16. S. R. Nicewarner-Peña, R. G. Freeman, B. D. Reiss, L. He, D. J. Peña, I. D. Walton, R. Cromer, C. D. Keating and M. J. Natan, *Science*, 2001, **294**, 137-141.
17. G. A. Ozin, I. Manners, S. Fournier-Bidoz and A. Arsenault, *Adv Mater*, 2005, **17**, 3011-3018.
18. D. Kagan, P. Calvo-Marzal, S. Balasubramanian, S. Sattayasamitsathit, K. M. Manesh, G.-U. Flechsig and J. Wang, *J Am Chem Soc*, 2009, **131**, 12082-12083.
19. Y. Mei, A. A. Solovev, S. Sanchez and O. G. Schmidt, *Chem Soc Rev*, 2011, **40**, 2109-2119.
20. J. Wang, *Micromachines: Fundamentals and Applications*. Wiley-VCH, 2013.
21. E. Karshalev, B. Esteban-Fernandez de Avila and J. Wang, *J Am Chem Soc*, 2018, **140**, 3810-3820.
22. J. Orozco, G. Pan, S. Sattayasamitsathit, M. Galarnyk and J. Wang, *Analyst*, 2015, **140**, 1421-1427.
23. J. Li, I. Rozen and J. Wang, *ACS Nano*, 2016, **10**, 5619-5634.
24. R. Maria-Hormigos, B. Jurado-Sanchez and A. Escarpa, *Lab Chip*, 2016, **16**, 2397-2407.
25. J. Wang, *Biosens Bioelectron*, 2016, **76**, 234-242.
26. B. Jurado-Sánchez and A. Escarpa, *Electroanalysis*, 2017, **29**, 14-23.
27. S. Campuzano, B. Esteban-Fernández de Ávila, P. Yáñez-Sedeño, J. M. Pingarrón and J. Wang, *Chem Sci*, 2017, **8**, 6750-6763.
28. C. C. Mayorga-Martinez and M. Pumera, *Adv Function Mater*, 2019, **30**, 1906449.
29. M. S. Draz, K. M. Kochehbyoki, A. Vasani, D. Battalapalli, A. Sreeram, M. K. Kanakasabapathy, S. Kallakuri, A. Tsibris, D. R. Kuritzkes and H. Shafiee, *Nat Commun*, 2018, **9**, 4282.
30. M. S. Draz, N. K. Lakshminaraasimulu, S. Krishnakumar, D. Battalapalli, A. Vasani, M. K. Kanakasabapathy, A. Sreeram, S. Kallakuri, P. Thirumalaraju, Y. Li, S. Hua, X. G. Yu, D. R. Kuritzkes and H. Shafiee, *ACS Nano*, 2018, **12**, 5709-5718.
31. K. Yuan, C. Cuntín-Abal, B. Jurado-Sánchez and A. Escarpa, *Anal Chem*, 2021, DOI: 10.1021/acs.analchem.1c02947.
32. B. Jurado-Sánchez, A. Escarpa and J. Wang, *Chem Commun*, 2015, **51**, 14088-14091.
33. M. Pacheco, B. Jurado-Sánchez and A. Escarpa, *Angew Chem Int Ed*, 2019, **58**, 18017-18024.
34. A. Jaiswal, S. S. Ghosh and A. Chattopadhyay, *Langmuir*, 2012, **28**, 15687-15696.
35. M. Pacheco, M. Á. López, B. Jurado-Sánchez and A. Escarpa, *Anal Bioanal Chem*, 2019, **411**, 6561-6573.
36. B. Esteban-Fernández de Ávila, M. A. Lopez-Ramirez, D. F. Báez, A. Jodra, V. V. Singh, K. Kaufmann and J. Wang, *ACS Sensors*, 2016, **1**, 217-221.
37. B. Esteban-Fernández de Ávila, A. Martín, F. Soto, M. A. Lopez-Ramirez, S. Campuzano, G. M. Vásquez-Machado, W. Gao, L. Zhang and J. Wang, *ACS Nano*, 2015, **9**, 6756-6764.
38. V. V. Singh, K. Kaufmann, B. E.-F. de Ávila, E. Karshalev and J. Wang, *Adv Function Mater*, 2016, **26**, 6270-6278.
39. K. Yuan, V. de la Asunción-Nadal, Y. Li, B. Jurado-Sánchez and A. Escarpa, *Chem Eur J*, 2020, **26**, 8471-8477.
40. J. Sanchez and J. Holmgren, *Indian J Med Res*, 2011, **133**, 153-163.
41. S. K. Lim, P. Chen, F. L. Lee, S. Mochhala and B. Liedberg, *Anal Chem*, 2015, **87**, 9408-9412.